

ISic0743

I.Sicily inscription 0743

Language

Latin

Type

seat

inscription

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Amphitheatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. loc[us] Aur[eli ---]

Apparatus

Text after Buonocore 1992 (EAOR)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175788

EDR 081531

EDCS 21900464

Bibliography

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